

The method has an added advantage that it is quicker and simpler as compared to conductometric and potentiometric methods and hence is recommended for quick analysis of thiocarbamides upto 10 mg.

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Analytical Applications of DEAPG as Gravimetric Reagent III : Estimation of Au(III)

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P-DIETHYLAMINOANIL of phenylglyoxal (abbreviated as DEAPG) precipitates gold(III) quantitatively and gives grey coloured complex in the pH range 5.0 ± 1.0 by adding double to triple theoretical quantity of the ligand. It can be used for the gravimetric estimation of Au(III) either alone or in the presence of foreign ions.

A perusal of literature on gravimetric analysis of metals reveals that many organic compounds have been used in the inorganic quantitative estimations but ketoanils¹⁻³ have been rarely employed as precipitating reagents. Moreover gravimetric estimations of noble metals⁴⁻⁸, viz., Au(III) etc have not been carried out to good extent. Some references⁹⁻¹⁰ on the gravimetric estimation of Au(III) are available but no attempt has been made in the quantitative estimation of this ion by employing ketoanil (DEAPG) as precipitating reagent so far. However, estimation of Hg(II) and Pt(IV) with this ligand have been done by authors¹¹⁻¹². The present paper aims at using the same ligand for the

gravimetric determination of Au(III). The work incorporated in this paper describes the suitable conditions for the precipitation of metal ions by the ligand.

Experimental

Stock solution of metal chloride (J. M. C., London) was prepared by dissolving pure compound in alcohol and was used after standardisation by standard methods¹³. Standard solution of ligand was prepared by dissolving its directly weighed quantity in the same medium. All the reagents and chemicals used were of either B.D.H. or E. Merck, A. R. and G. R. grades respectively. Ligand was prepared by method reported by Verma¹⁴.

The pH of the solution was adjusted by using hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide. A Phillips pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements. G4-sintered glass crucibles (JENA) were used for gravimetric estimations.

In the gravimetric estimations Au(III) chloride solution was diluted with double distilled water ten times to the initial volume before adding the precipitant. Reagent solution was added very slowly with constant stirring to the metal chloride solution till in slight excess. The quantitative reaction was ensured by adjusting pH with alcoholic solution of acid and alkali. Reaction mixture was left for four hours and was collected on sintered glass crucible. The precipitate of the complex was washed with ether till free from excess reagent and was dried to constant weight.

Au(III) - DEAPG complex was found soluble in acetone alcohol and methyl cyanide but insoluble in benzene, petroleum ether, carbon-tetrachloride and ether. It was decomposed by conc. nitric and sulphuric acids.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH, reagent concentration and temperature :

The effect of pH, ligand concentration and temperature has been observed with 4.0 ml of metal chloride solution containing 19.126 mg metal. A perusal of data reveals that the weights of the precipitate were almost corresponding to the theoretical values of Au(III) - DEAPG complex at pH 5.0 ± 1.0 in the temperature range of 100-110° by the addition of double to triple theoretical quantity of the ligand. Grey coloured complex $[\text{Au}(\text{DEAPG})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}_2$ was found stable above 180°

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Quantitative gravimetric estimation :

Under the above mentioned conditions of pH, reagent concentration and temperature gravimetric estimations of different quantities of Au(III) were done. The conversion factor for complex to metal is 0.3376.

Effect of foreign ions :

There was no interference by the addition of different quantities of foreign ions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CH_3COO^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cd^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Hg^{+2}) on the precipitation of Au(III) done in suitable conditions.

There are certain cations like Fe(III), Cu(II), Pt(IV) which interfered in the estimation of Au(III).

In the light of above facts reagent DEAPG may be recommended as a promising gravimetric reagent for gold(III).

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Paper and Cellulose Thin Layer Chromatography of Toxic Cations

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CLEAR separations of toxic cations¹⁻⁵ :—Ce(IV), Ni(II), Cu(II), Bi(III), Hg(II), Tl(I), Pb(II), Be(II) and As(V) were achieved by ascending paper and cellulose thin layer chromatography in solvents: (1) Ethyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : methyl ethyl ketone : chloroform : 12N. HCl (25 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 10); (2) Ethyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : chloroform : methyl ethyl ketone : 12N. HCl (20 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 15) and (3) Isopropyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : acetone : chloroform : 12N. HCl (25 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 10). The order of R_f values is : $\text{Hg} > \text{As} > \text{Bi} > \text{Cu} > \text{Pb} > \text{Ni} > \text{Ce} > \text{Be}$, Tl. The differential mobility and separation of cations is based on differential solubilization of their chlorocomplexes in these polar solvents.

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Maleianilic Acids as Derivatives for Characterization of Aromatic Primary Amines and Their Paper Chromatographic Detection and Separation

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AROMATIC primary amines were characterized in qualitative analysis by formation of corresponding maleianilic acids as derivatives. The maleianilic acids were obtained in pure state and in good yield and have sharp melting points. The corresponding maleianilic acids were detected and separated using paper chromatography. The coloured spots were clearly visible while rest were visualized in iodine vapours.

Subba Rao characterized some aromatic primary amines as a derivative of corresponding phthalanilic